

Methods for improving balance maintenance mechanisms in young boxers

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¹Majidov Ruslan Rustam ugli

¹Fergana state university, Fergana, Uzbekistan

Abstract

This article scientifically examines the issues of improving the balance maintenance mechanism during movement in young boxers engaged in the sport of boxing. The study analyzed young athletes' physical fitness, vestibular stability, coordination abilities, and balance level during the execution of technical and tactical movements. The effectiveness of implementing special exercises, balance-developing methods, and modern training tools into the training process was evaluated. The results of conducted pedagogical experiments and control tests showed significant improvement in balance maintenance indicators among young boxers. Based on the research results, practical recommendations for coaches were developed, and the importance of balance-focused training in the preparation process of young boxers was scientifically substantiated.

Keywords: balance maintenance, vestibular apparatus, deficit, nervous system, simplicity, accessibility, static balance, dynamic balance, standing position.

Introduction

Currently, the analysis and results of experimental tests conducted within the framework of the research topic have shown that insufficient attention is paid to the program of exercises for maintaining balance during movement in boxing. Accordingly, during the formative experiment process, basic academic training was organized with the introduction of a set of balance exercises for young boxers. This enhances the emotional aspect of the conducted training sessions and helps to consider the assessment of individual characteristics in the development of young boxers' physiques. Boxing is a dynamic sport with a high time deficit, where each action of the athlete (attack, defense, feint) is associated with a change in the body's center of gravity. The mechanism of maintaining balance is primarily a result of the complex integration of the central nervous system, vestibular apparatus, visual analyzers, and musculoskeletal sensations. The importance of this mechanism in young boxers is doubled, as

at this age, the acceleration of height growth shifts the body's center of gravity upwards, which is considered a period leading to decreased stability, thus requiring their training during this time.

Objective of the study: To analyze the improvement of the balance maintenance mechanism when performing various movements in young people engaged in boxing.

Research objectives: Young boxers' balance is considered in two main states, namely static balance and dynamic balance. Static balance refers to athletes maintaining body stability in a relatively motionless state (for example, when occupying a position). In boxing, static balance serves as a "platform" for delivering a powerful punch, and if the static balance in the boxer's legs is disrupted, the force of the punch can decrease by 30-40%. Dynamic balance is the ability to quickly restore body balance during movement, especially after delivering a strike or when avoiding an opponent's strike. Dynamic balance determines the boxer's "ring sense" and the speed of entering the fight. Methods of comprehensive balance assessment: In the experimental part of the scientific work, it is recommended to use the following assessment systems.

Results and discussions

Currently, the generally accepted system of basic physical and special training for young boxers consists of three parts, in which the interconnected tasks defined in the physical and special training program are addressed.

For the maximum effectiveness of the balance exercise method (regardless of which variant is used), the following rules must be observed:

- simplicity, accessibility, and safety;
- repeatability and cyclicality;
- consistency and comprehensiveness of exercises;
- alternating between load and rest;

Load standardization amount.

Adhering to the principles of simplicity, accessibility, and safety involves selecting a methodology (program) for implementing a set of balance exercises suitable for young boxers. This set should consist of relatively simple, technically uncomplicated exercises that, if possible, do not require additional protection (spotting) from the coach or training partner. In such cases, young boxers can focus on mastering the fundamental physical exercises without being distracted by complex techniques, allowing them to perfect their motor skills.

The rule of repetition and cyclicity requires that the selected exercises in the set remain unchanged for 4-5 training sessions, with each exercise being performed repeatedly, similar to cyclic movements (after which they can be partially or completely replaced).

The rule of standardization (quantity) in the balance training complex typically involves the ability to sufficiently adjust or reduce the workload, taking into account the boxer's age, health status, and level of preparedness, depending on the assigned task. Based on the level of physical and special training of young boxers, the coach can assign either a uniform workload for the entire group or individually tailored loads with different characteristics for specific boxers, using each set of balance exercises.

The body of young boxers gradually adapts to regular and systematically recurring physical loads. Therefore, when performing this complex of exercises, it is necessary to gradually increase the load through the planned exercise norms. Each exercise is repeated unchanged for 2-3 training sessions. In the final session, to identify and encourage improvements in the boxers' performance, it is recommended to retest the highest score for each exercise and compare it with the initial results.

The coach should allocate time for exercises and carry a stopwatch to measure heart rate. Heart rate should be recorded immediately before performing the set of exercises and after completing balance exercises, then immediately after and at two-minute intervals for 10 minutes (the number of beats per minute is calculated by multiplying the result by 6). Heart rate readings are recorded on the young boxer's personal card (which is kept by the instructor).

The heart rate counting begins as soon as the young boxer prepares to perform the

exercises. The coach should teach young boxers in advance how to independently measure their heart rate.

Recording heart rate allows monitoring the body's response to the proposed physical exertion. Boxers whose heart rate exceeds 170 beats per minute after performing exercises are advised to rest before engaging in high-intensity exercises and then proceed with the next exercise.

Regular and systematic evaluation of the highest test results, as well as consideration of the workload, enables the coach to draw conclusions about the improvement of the body's performance capacity. Comparing the heart rate response to a standard load (a set of exercises repeated several times during training) allows for conclusions about the cardiovascular system's adaptation to these exercises. Improvement in its regulation is reflected in a rapid decrease in heart rate after a standard load. All of this ensures precise coaching control and independent self-monitoring of the body's corresponding reactions by young boxers.

It is recommended to start with the 3rd or 4th training session after young boxers are better prepared to perform tasks such as determining the maximum test, assigning individual workloads, counting heart rates, and recording results in personal cards. During these training sessions, the level of physical development and functional capabilities of the boxers' bodies will have significantly adapted. The role of individual tasks in training increases, which confirms the necessity of determining the highest test for each boxer when performing exercises using the balance exercise method.

In many cases, if certain muscle groups of one boxer's body are working predominantly, it forces the partner's muscles to work in the opposing exercise. This complex can be used throughout the annual training cycle for the purpose of harmoniously developing the main muscle groups in terms of strength and strength endurance of the body.

This set of exercises can be performed for 3-5 months with boxers who have completed the initial training period and have achieved a sufficient level of preparedness.

Many exercises in this complex, when performed at the highest speed and in moderate repetitions, create a foundation for developing movement speed. They allow for isolated targeting to develop strength in almost all main

Table. Analysis indicators of post-experimental results for young boxers in the experimental and control groups with different physical development n=50

No.	Control tests	At the beginning of the experiment			At the end of the experiment			Relative growth, %	t	P
		\bar{X}	σ	V %	\bar{X}	σ	V %			
Experimental group										
1	60 m run (sec)	9.8	0.68	7.08	8.8	0.56	6.37	8.33	4.44	<0.001
2	3x10 shuttle run (sec)	8.0	0.55	6.89	7.6	0.52	6.84	5.0	2.65	<0.05
3	Jump rope (1 min) (times)	90.0	5.89	6.54	101	4.88	4.83	12.22	7.19	<0.001
4	Pull-ups (times)	6.0	0.46	7.66	7.0	0.35	5.00	16.67	9.09	<0.001
5	3000 m run (min.sec)	15.30	1.26	8.23	14.40	0.98	6.80	5.88	2.19	<0.05
6	Standing long jump (m.cm)	170	7.95	4.68	180	4.86	2.70	5.89	5.37	<0.001
7	Forward bend from the gymnastics bench without bending knees (measured below feet level, cm)	+6	0.46	7.67	+7	0.41	5.86	16.67	8.33	<0.001
8	Standing on one leg with eyes open and closed (30-60 sec), (sec) static balance	20.0	1.98	9.90	14.5	1.01	6.96	27.5	12.50	<0.001
9	Number of deviations when walking 5-10 meters along a 10 cm wide beam (cm.meter) dynamic balance	3.0	0.18	6.0	2.2	0.15	6.82	26.67	17.02	<0.001
10	Vestibular test: 10 quick spins in place followed by walking in a straight line (cm)	25.0	2.13	8.52	19.5	1.87	9.58	22.0	9.70	<0.001
11	10 quick rotations in place followed by walking sideways in a straight line (cm)	26.0	1.43	5.50	19.2	1.16	8.44	26.15	17.66	<0.001
12	10 quick turns in place followed by walking backwards (cm)	30.0	2.77	9.23	18.5	1.89	10.22	38.33	27.61	<0.001
13	Body center displacement (mm)	11.0	0.68	5.64	6.5	0.66	10.15	40.91	24.86	<0.001
Control group										
1	60 m run (sec)	9.7	0.87	8.97	9.8	0.98	10.00	1.03	0.39	>0.05
2	Shuttle run 3x10 (s)	8.1	0.64	7.90	8.2	0.69	8.41	1.23	0.53	>0.05
3	Skipping rope (times)	91.0	4.99	5.48	90.5	4.40	4.86	0.55	0.37	>0.05
4	Pull-ups (times)	6.2	0.57	8.76	6.5	0.67	10.30	4.84	1.70	>0.05
5	3000 m run (min.s)	15.55	1.46	9.39	15.42	1.58	10.25	0.84	0.30	>0.05
6	Standing long jump (m.cm)	165.0	8.63	5.23	166.5	9.05	5.43	0.91	0.60	>0.05
7	Forward bend from a gymnastics bench without bending knees (measured below foot level, cm)	+6.20	0.52	8.39	+6.3	0.68	8.10	1.61	0.59	>0.05
8	Standing on one leg with eyes open and closed (30-60 seconds), (seconds), static balance	20.50	1.11	5.41	20.65	1.21	5.86	0.73	0.46	>0.05
9	Number of deviations when walking 5-10 meters along a 10 cm wide beam (cm.meter), dynamic balance	3.1	0.25	7.14	3.2	0.18	5.62	3.22	1.62	>0.05
10	10 quick spins in place followed by walking in a straight line (cm)	25.5	2.24	8.78	24.8	2.45	9.88	2.74	0.92	>0.05
11	10 quick rotations in place followed by walking sideways in a straight line (cm)	25.5	2.56	10.04	24.3	2.68	11.02	4.70	1.62	>0.05
12	10 quick turns in place followed by walking backwards (cm)	31.0	2.76	8.90	29.8	2.01	6.74	3.87	1.76	>0.05
13	Body center displacement (mm)	11.5	0.83	7.22	11.01	0.95	8.63	4.26	1.96	>0.05

muscle groups of the body. The simplicity and accessibility of these exercises make them suitable for successful application by boxers of all skill levels.

The volume of physical loads in the main part of the training is distributed as follows: 35-40% of the time is allocated for developing basic physical and special qualities, while 15-20% is for correcting insufficiently developed

motor qualities.

This set of exercises can be used during sports training sessions.

Changing and managing the arrangement of loads and exercises in this and subsequent exercise sets is carried out according to the rules and procedures for conducting balance exercises described above.

The effectiveness of the observed changes

lies in the fact that the content of physical training sessions was determined taking into account the individual characteristics of boxers, which ensured the development of physical and special qualities, as well as the physical fitness of young boxers engaged in the sport of boxing.

Following the pedagogical experiment with young boxers, exercises for maintaining balance and accounting for individual body weight, as well as paired exercises, were widely implemented. During each training session, the functional state of the boxers was monitored using objective and subjective indicators.

The indicators of young boxers' physical and special qualities are presented in the following tables (see Table).

The difference in the indicators of young boxers in the experimental group for physical and special training control tests at the beginning and end of the experiment was as follows. The 60m run averaged 9.8 seconds at the beginning of the experiment and 8.8 seconds at the end of the experiment (difference of 1.0 second), with a relative increase of 8.33% $P < 0.001$.

The 3x10 shuttle run showed an average of 8.0 seconds at the beginning of the experiment and an average of 7.6 seconds at the end of the experiment (difference of 0.4 seconds), a relative increase of 5.0% $P < 0.05$. Skipping rope jumps averaged 90.0 times at the beginning of the experiment and 101.0 times at the end of the experiment (difference of 11.0 times), with a relative increase of 12.22% $P < 0.001$. Pull-ups on the horizontal bar averaged 6.0 times at the beginning of the experiment and 7.0 times at the end of the experiment (difference of 1.0 time), the relative increase was 16.67% $P < 0.001$. The 3000m run averaged 15.30 minutes at the beginning of the experiment and 14.40 minutes at the end of the experiment (difference of 0.9 minutes), a relative increase of 5.88% $P < 0.05$.

The standing long jump averaged 170.0 centimeters at the beginning of the experiment and 180.0 centimeters at the end (a difference of 10.0 centimeters), with a relative increase of 5.89% ($P < 0.001$). Forward bending from a gymnastic bench without bending the knees averaged +6.0 centimeters at the beginning of the experiment and +7.0 centimeters at the end (a difference of +1.0 centimeters), with a relative increase of 16.67% ($P < 0.001$). Standing on one leg with eyes open and closed averaged 20.0 seconds at the beginning of the experiment and 14.5 seconds at the end (a difference of 5.5 seconds), with a relative

decrease of 27.5% ($P < 0.001$). Walking 5-10 meters along a 10 cm wide beam had an average deviation of 3.0 centimeters at the beginning of the experiment, improving to 2.2 centimeters at the end (a difference of 0.8 centimeters), with a relative improvement of 26.67% ($P < 0.001$). Walking in a straight line after 10 quick turns in place averaged 25.0 centimeters of deviation at the beginning of the experiment and 19.5 centimeters at the end (a difference of 5.5 centimeters), with a relative improvement of 22.0% ($P < 0.001$). Walking sideways after 10 quick turns in place averaged 26.0 centimeters of deviation at the beginning of the experiment and 19.2 centimeters at the end (a difference of 6.8 centimeters), showing a relative improvement of 26.15% ($P < 0.001$). Walking backward after 10 quick turns in place averaged 30.0 centimeters of deviation at the beginning of the experiment and 18.5 centimeters at the end (a difference of 11.5 centimeters), with a relative improvement of 38.33% ($P < 0.001$). The displacement of the body's center of gravity averaged 11.0 millimeters at the beginning of the experiment and 6.5 millimeters at the end (a difference of 4.5 millimeters), showing a relative improvement of 40.91% ($P < 0.001$).

The difference in the indicators of young boxers in the control group for physical and special training tests at the beginning and end of the experiment was as follows. The 60m run averaged 9.7 seconds at the beginning of the experiment and 9.8 seconds at the end (difference of 0.1 seconds), with a relative increase of 1.03% ($P > 0.05$). The 3x10 shuttle run averaged 8.1 seconds at the beginning and 8.2 seconds at the end (difference of 0.1 seconds), showing a relative increase of 1.23% ($P > 0.05$). Jump rope skipping averaged 91.0 times at the beginning and 90.5 times at the end (difference of 0.5 times), with a relative increase of 0.55% ($P > 0.05$). Pull-ups on a horizontal bar averaged 6.2 times at the beginning and 6.5 times at the end (difference of 0.3 times), with a relative increase of 4.84% ($P > 0.05$). The 3000m run averaged 15.55 minutes at the beginning and 15.42 minutes at the end (difference of 0.13 minutes), a relative increase of 0.84% ($P > 0.05$). The standing long jump averaged 165.0 centimeters at the beginning and 166.5 centimeters at the end (difference of 1.5 centimeters), with a relative increase of 0.91% ($P > 0.05$). Forward bending from a gymnastics bench without bending the knees averaged +6.20 cm at the beginning and +6.30 cm at the end (difference of +0.1 cm), with a relative increase of 1.61% ($P > 0.05$). Standing on

one leg with eyes open and closed averaged 20.50 seconds at the beginning and 20.65 seconds at the end (difference of 0.15 seconds), with a relative increase of 0.73% ($P>0.05$). Walking 5-10 meters along a 10 cm wide beam with deviations (cm) averaged 3.1 centimeters at the beginning and improved to 3.2 centimeters at the end (difference of 0.1 centimeters), showing a relative increase of 3.22% ($P>0.05$).

Walking in a straight line after 10 quick turns in place averaged 25.5 centimeters of deviation at the beginning and 24.8 centimeters at the end (difference of 0.7 centimeters), with a relative increase of 2.74% ($P>0.05$). Walking sideways after 10 quick turns in place averaged 25.5 centimeters of deviation at the beginning and 24.3 centimeters at the end (difference of 1.2 centimeters), showing a relative increase of 4.70% ($P>0.05$). Walking backward after 10 quick turns in place averaged 31.0 centimeters of deviation at the beginning and 29.8 centimeters at the end (difference of 1.2 centimeters), with a relative increase of 3.87% ($P>0.05$). The displacement of the body's center of mass averaged 11.5 millimeters at the beginning and 11.01 millimeters at the end (difference of 0.49 millimeters), showing a relative increase of 4.26% ($P>0.05$).

Conclusion

In the research process involving the experimental group of young boxers, it is necessary to implement exercise programs focusing on balance-maintaining exercises during sports training. When comparing the results at the beginning and end of the study for physical fitness indicators of the young boxers involved in the research, particularly in terms of coordination, agility, and endurance, it was found that after implementing the balance exercise program, the physical fitness indicators increased by an average of 23.07% compared to the beginning of the study. This improvement is statistically significant ($P<0.001$).

During the study, when students in the control group continued training based on the traditional state program, it was found that the results showed only a slight increase when comparing indicators at the beginning and end of the experiment. This improvement was not statistically significant ($P>0.05$).

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY:

**Ruslan
Rustam ugli
MAJIDOV**

Employment

Lecturer at Fergana state university

Degree

MD

Research interests

Boxing, professional athlete's, physical education and sport, Theory of physical education, Analyzing of sport competitions.

Email:

ruslanmajidov5732@gmail.com